

Project information

Project full title	LEAPS pilot to foster open innovation for accelerator-based light sources in Europe
Project acronym	LEAPS-INNOV
Grant agreement no.	101004728
Instrument	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Duration	01/04/2021 – 31/03/2025
Website	www.leaps-innov.eu/

Deliverable information

Deliverable no.	D8.4
Deliverable title	Industry engagement in the context of instrumentation: worked case study booklet
Deliverable responsible	ULUND
Related Work-Package/Task	WP8: Task 8.1.1
Type (e.g. Report; other)	Digital publication (pdf)
Author(s)	Shandana Mufti, Magnus Larsson
Dissemination level	public
Document Version	1
Date	11.07.2025
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Document information

Version no.	Date	Author(s)	Comment
1	11.07.2025	Shandana Mufti, Magnus Larsson	

D8.4 – LEAPS-INNOV Booklet: Industry Engagement in the Context of Instrumentation

This deliverable presents a curated collection of case studies developed under the LEAPS-INNOV project. The booklet highlights successful examples of early-stage collaboration, co-design, knowledge transfer, and innovation procurement between research infrastructures and industry.

Each case study illustrates how strategic partnerships have driven technological advancements in areas such as detector systems, X-ray optics, positioning systems, insertion devices, and data management. The publication showcases the value of industry engagement in addressing key challenges in instrumentation development and offers practical insights into fostering sustainable innovation ecosystems, but also highlights some of the challenges in the process.

By documenting these experiences, the booklet aims to inspire future collaborations and strengthen Europe's leadership in photon science and innovation.

Annex

Case study booklet

Industry Engagement in the Context of Instrumentation

WORKED CASE STUDY BOOKLET

LEAPS FACILITIES AND PARTNERS

The League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources, LEAPS, is a strategic consortium of 19 synchrotron radiation and free-electron laser user facilities across Europe. Their core mission is to elevate the quality and influence of fundamental, applied, and industrial research at each facility, amplifying the benefits for European science, innovation, and society as a whole.

ALBA - Barcelona (Spain)

DESY - PETRA III and FLASH - Hamburg (Germany)

Diamond Light Source - Didcot (United Kingdom)

Elettra - Trieste (Italy)

ESRF - Grenoble (France)

European XFEL - Schenefeld (Germany)

FELIX - Nijmegen (Netherlands)

HZB - BESSY II - Berlin (Germany)

HZDR - ELBE - Dresden (Germany)

INFN - Rome (Italy)

ISA - ASTRID2 - Aarhus (Denmark)

MAX IV - Lund (Sweden)

PSI - SLS and SwissFEL - Villigen (Switzerland)

PTB - Metrology Light Source - Berlin (Germany)

SESAME - Allan (Jordan)

SOLARIS - Krakow (Poland)

SOLEIL - Paris (France)

Vision

A world where European science is a catalyst for solving global challenges, a key driver for competitiveness and a compelling force for closer integration and peace through scientific collaboration.

Mission

LEAPS will use the power of its combined voice to ensure that member light source facilities continue to be world-leading, to act as a powerful tool for the development and integration of skills with a view to address 21st century global challenges, and to consolidate Europe's leadership in the field.

DRIVING INNOVATION THROUGH FACILITY-INDUSTRY PARTNERSHIPS

With more than 30,000 users, Europe's synchrotrons and free-electron lasers serve a vast scientific community. The science generated here spans fields from quantum physics and sustainable steel production to pharmaceutical development and plant-based food innovation.

In response to global competition, the League of European Accelerator-Based Photon Sources (LEAPS) brings together Europe's light source facilities to coordinate efforts and advance shared technological development.

Under the LEAPS-INNOV pilot project, nearly 20 European facilities joined forces to address key technological and supply chain challenges facing accelerator-based photon science. At the heart of this effort lies close collaboration with industry, an essential driver of innovation and resilience.

From the development of next-generation detector systems to more efficient data compression techniques, the work carried out within LEAPS-INNOV demonstrates how strategic partnerships can accelerate innovation and enhance the competitiveness of both European industry and research infrastructures.

This booklet presents a series of case studies that offer practical insights into early-stage collaboration, co-design, knowledge transfer, and innovation procurement.

Together, these cases illustrate diverse pathways to successful industry engagement in instrumentation development, with the aim of sparking new ideas for sustainable collaboration across the LEAPS community and beyond.

Together we are stronger
Together we work on solutions

“SYNCHROTRON SCIENCE
THRIVES WHEN RESEARCH
FACILITIES AND INDUSTRY
WORK HAND IN HAND.”

SASCHA GRIMM, DECTRIS

ADVANCING GERMANIUM DETECTORS FOR MODERN BEAMLINES

WORK PACKAGE 2

Led by SOLEIL Synchrotron and Diamond Light Source, Work Package 2 was tasked with the development of next-generation Germanium detectors. These detectors have been left largely underdeveloped despite their importance in X-ray spectroscopy. They detect high-energy photons efficiently without producing signals that interfere with the accurate measurements.

To push detector performance to the next level and keep them on par with new beamlines and photon sources, a focus of the project was improving the number of photons per square millimetre that a detector can handle. This required the development of compact multi-element detectors with tiny front-end electronics and advanced signal processing.

Credit: SOLEIL Synchrotron
Images of the different detector parts developed within LEAPS WP2

Industry involvement began early in the process, with one company signing on to deliver germanium sensors. Through a tender process run by SOLEIL, another company won the contract to build a new, complex electronics chain with integration and interface management. The mechanical design was an iterative process during which simulations were run repeatedly to test the detector's response to X-rays. The completed detector delivers a high X-ray throughput and works in a wide energy range (from 5 to 100 keV). It includes a cryostat, a cooling system, and an electronics housing.

The prototype was assembled at ESRF, where the first test beam took place, before further testing at SOLEIL.

Credit: SOLEIL Synchrotron
The XAFS-DET prototype during the characterisation test

Key Lessons

While the hope was that several industry partners would be contracted to provide germanium sensors, ultimately, it came down to only one. This highlights the need for more suppliers and industry partners who can meet the growing demands of Europe's light sources, especially as they continue to develop higher-energy and higher-precision beams.

SUPERFLAT: SMOOTHER SURFACES, SHARPER LIGHT

WORK PACKAGE 3

At LEAPS facilities, the quality of mirrors, which are key optical elements at beamlines, has remained a limiting factor in the quality of beams that can be delivered. These mirrors are used to focus and steer light, select specific wavelengths for experiments, and improve the coherence of a beam.

Through LEAPS-INNOV, the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility and SOLEIL Synchrotron led Work Package 3, which conducted a Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) to enable European companies to produce these mirrors. The aim was to develop processes for fabricating flat mirrors with curves of less than one nanometre, slope errors under 50 nanoradians, and surface roughness of less than 1 Ångström, while also studying how mirror shapes can be corrected. A related goal was the creation of metrology methods and protocols for use in factories where these mirrors are produced in order to guarantee the highest degrees of accuracy.

Credit: Work Package 3

The Benefits of PCP

While the implementation of a PCP process can be complex, it brings valuable outcomes. Vendors were chosen through a competitive tender process, with three companies awarded different contracts through the phases of the project. By outsourcing research and development through PCP, the Superflat group exploited the expertise that already exists in Europe's facilities and industry, and provided financial support to both companies and researchers. A big advantage of this process is that risks and opportunities are shared by public buyers and private suppliers, creating an environment in which challenges are met and innovation thrives.

<https://leaps-superflat.eu>

NEXTGRATING: PRECISION FABRICATION IN X-RAY OPTICS

WORK PACKAGE 4

Used at both synchrotrons and free-electron lasers, X-ray diffraction gratings are key optical elements that allow researchers to separate and analyse X-ray beams by wavelength which is essential at soft- and tender-X-ray-beamlines in spectroscopy and X-ray microscopy applications. When the beams hit the grooves etched onto the grating's surface at a specific angle, they are reflected into different directions depending on their wavelength.

Credit: Work Package 4

Work Package 4, led by the Paul Scherrer Institute and Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin, sought to empower more industry partners, specifically small and medium enterprises, to produce blazed gratings by means of electron-beam lithography. This technique offers patterning on the nanometre scale, producing extremely precise diffractive elements like gratings or reflection zone plates. Through close collaboration with industrial and academic partners, the group has developed an e-beam lithography-based process for producing blazed gratings with variable line spacing on curved substrates of up to 140mm in length and 10mm in thickness. This development included the upgrade of software and hardware components essential for efficient and precise writing of full-sized gratings. The quality of the gratings was confirmed by various metrology methods and tests at both synchrotrons and free-electron laser sources.

Credit: Work Package 4

DELIVERING ACCURACY: FROM NANOSCALE SCANNING TO BEAM SYNCHRONISATION

WORK PACKAGE 5

Efficient sample delivery continues to pose challenges to all fields in x-ray photon science. Work Package 5 tackled several tasks related to improving the speed and accuracy of scanning systems.

The first task was the development of new devices for sample scanning on the nanoscale. Through a competitive dialogue procedure with a company, the collaborators successfully tested a magnetic levitation demonstrator stage offering high accuracy monitoring with sample rotation and translation.

High resolution metrology is another challenge in synchrotron experiments, and in collaboration with two industry partners, the group developed two demonstrators using different concepts. Finally, the group also collaborated with a company in the synchrotron radiation field to develop a protocol for synchronising experimental equipment with the high frequency structure of the beams at LEAPS light sources.

The group was led by Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin and Diamond Light Source.

Credit: Credit: Kenneth Ruona
MAX IV's NanoMax beamline

LEAPS INSERTION DEVICES: TURNING EXPERTISE INTO INNOVATION

WORK PACKAGE 6

With a strong emphasis on knowledge and technology transfer from facilities to industry, Work Package 6 highlights how these transfers kickstart cutting-edge innovation and lay the groundwork for productive partnerships.

For technologies at a low Technology Readiness Level, early-stage knowledge transfer is particularly valuable. Engaging new providers at this stage equips them with the expertise needed to participate effectively in future calls for tender and contribute to the development of innovative solutions.

Led by SOLEIL Synchrotron, the Paul Scherrer Institute, and Elettra Synchrotron, the group set out to push the limits of Insertion Device technology. Their goal was to produce high performing undulators that are more compact and cheaper than present models. Four prototypes were commissioned:

- HTS Superconducting Undulator
- Cryogenic Permanent Magnet Undulator
- Cryogenic APPLE III Undulator
- APPLE X Undulator

In addition, two specialised measurement benches were developed to characterise the performance of these devices.

A key lesson learned was that successful collaborations require bilateral engagement. Interactions between facilities and industry flourish not only in formal meetings but also in workshops and networking events facilitated by the LEAPS consortium. Mapping out key stakeholders can also streamline this process through targeted matchmaking of researchers and companies.

Key Developments

At MAX IV, the researchers who design and installed a full-scale APPLE X undulator prototype have published their design specifications, fabrication process, and implementation. They are prepared for a technology transfer with an industrial partner.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016890022401088X?via%3Dihub>

At PSI, researchers are developing a high-temperature superconducting undulator that will be installed at the Swiss Light Source storage ring. They are seeking an industrial partner for knowledge transfer.

<https://www.bsf2024.org/technology-transfer-track-posters/paul-scherrer-institute-technology-transfer-track-posters/>

At SOLEIL, researchers from the synchrotron and ESRF have built a cryogenic permanent magnet undulator, and have an open call for partnership.

<https://www.bsf2024.org/technology-transfer-track-posters/synchrotron-soleil-technology-transfer-track-posters/>

Credit: Tarawneh, H., Holz, M., and Roslund, L., 2024.
Apple X Prototype

SMART DATA HANDLING FOR EUROPE'S PHOTON SOURCES

WORK PACKAGE 7

Work Package 7, led by MAX IV Laboratory and DESY, partnered with industry to create open-source tools for managing the large volumes of data generated at European photon sources. After a survey of light source needs, the group was able to determine which problems were most pressing.

Featuring both knowledge transfers and technology alignments between facilities and industry, as well as collaboration on solutions to tackle data volumes, the group developed methods that can be implemented in data compression and handling.

The group received sample data from a detector producing company, which helped in the process of aligning facility technologies with those of industrial partners. This data was used as a testing ground for compression protocols.

The group's key collaboration was with a company with expertise in Blosc2, a super-fast data compression library. With this partner, the development and testing of a compression algorithm compatible with the data being produced by LEAPS facilities, was completed, tested, and implemented.

A final partner was a company dealing in open source data management technology, including the data format that was used in the implementation of the compression codec.

Industrial partners were crucial to every step of the process here, and were deeply embedded into the work of the facilities. Through this knowledge exchanged and intense collaboration, solutions were developed and have also been made available to non-LEAPS members.

<https://gitlab.com/leaps-innov-wp7/>

Credit: Work package 7
Data reduction and compression with Blosc

"HOW TO DEVELOP SUCH A THING IS BY BREAKING THE BIGGER PROBLEM INTO SMALLER PHASES – AND THAT'S EXACTLY WHAT THE COMPETITIVE DIALOGUE DOES."

RONALD SCHNEIDER, MI-PARTNERS

"TOGETHER, WE ADDRESS REAL-WORLD CHALLENGES IN SYNCHROTRON SCIENCE – FROM DETECTOR DATA RATES TO DATA COMPRESSION AND STANDARDISATION – ENABLING MORE EFFICIENT COMPUTING WORKFLOWS AND BETTER SCIENTIFIC OUTCOMES. AT DECTRIS, I SEE THIS TECHNOLOGY ALIGNMENT AS A FOUNDATION FOR SUSTAINABLE AND INNOVATIVE RESEARCH ACROSS EUROPE."

SASCHA GRIMM, DECTRIS

"WE WERE PARTICULARLY IMPRESSED WITH THE CREATIVE AND EFFICIENT APPROACH TO ENGAGING OUR SERVICES, ENABLING US TO DELIVER RESULTS IN A VERY SHORT TIMEFRAME."

FRANCESC ALTED, IRONARRAY SLU

LESSONS LEARNED

When Europe's research infrastructures and industry work side by side, innovation thrives. From detector systems to data compression, each of the LEAPS-INNOV work packages highlights how early collaboration, shared expertise, and structured partnerships lead to tangible, real-world solutions.

Key lessons also emerged from this project, including the importance of competitive IP dialogues that may bolster industry engagement with publicly funded projects. Innovation procurement methods like PCP are powerful, but administratively heavy. Networking remains a crucial tool in making sure the right partners find each other.

And as the demands on Europe's photon science facilities continue to grow, our capacity to collaborate must keep up.

The partnerships formed through LEAPS-INNOV offer a clear path forward: one where science and industry shape the future together.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The LEAPS consortium is very grateful for the support provided by the National Funding Agencies as well as by the European Commission. Without their generous funding, the work of LEAPS and its participating facilities would not be possible. Collaborations with other nationally funded research institutions and universities further enrich the work of the consortium and ensure that the research done at LEAPS facilities and by LEAPS partners is societally relevant and impactful.

LEAPS also gratefully acknowledges the role of the scientific users of the facilities, whose capacity, diversity of interests, approaches and expertise, not to mention their scientific excellence, have helped drive the output and impact and have helped fulfil our mutual responsibilities in

many societally relevant areas. LEAPS also acknowledges the facility user organisations, the national user organisations, and the European user organisation ESUO, who have all been partners in our activities within the facility at the national scale, upwards to the European scale, and beyond.

LEAPS facilities acknowledge the support provided to scientific users by the European Commission and the decades of support in the form of successive Framework Programmes for Integrating Activities, and thank the Commission on behalf of our user communities for enabling the transnational access to our facilities.

The LEAPS-INNOV consortium was funded through Horizon 2020, grant agreement 101004728.

Strengthen Europe's leading role in science and innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101004728.

LEAPS

League of European
Accelerator-based
Photon Sources

<https://www.leaps-innov.eu>

<https://www.leaps-initiative.eu>